

Car Rental Portal

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Abstract—

In this study, a tradable permit mechanism for a car sharing system was proposed. Car sharing services that allow users to move freely decrease the efficiency of sharing vehicle use due to the uneven distribution of vehicles and origin-destination (OD) the usage fee for leaving the origin sharing station and the income for arriving at the destination sharing station. Additionally, the demands. The usage fee for leaving the origin sharing station and the income for arriving at the destination sharing station. Additionally, the findings indicated that the negative price of using mobility sharing could occur when there was high asymmetric imbalanced OD demand.

Keywords: Car Sharing; Tradable Permits; Combinatorial Auctions From the computational time viewpoint.

I. INTRODUCTION

The physical limitation of public street space is a challenge shared by cities world-wide. Increasing car ownership leads to parking problems and often to the misuse of sidewalks for parking. Congestion is another effect of having too many cars on limited street space.¹ Recent advances in information technology have led to the development of new

transportation services that aim to replace private cars. One of these approaches includes “mobility sharing” such as car and bicycle sharing. However, if the service allows users to move freely, then it decreases the efficiency of sharing vehicle use due to imbalances in distribution of vehicles and origin-destination (OD) demands. Additionally, it is not possible to achieve the goal of replacing private cars. A very common solution involves vehicle relocation in which drivers are employed to relocate vehicles to high demand sharing ports. However, it significantly increases the operational cost of the service providers. In this study, the introduction of tradable permits was proposed to optimize the efficiency of mobility sharing Systems. Such tradable permit schemes allow policy goals to be achieved without requiring monitoring of the value that users place on their time or on transportation services. Problem definition the car inspection starts when the car is admitted to the inspection place, the employee walks around the car to check if there are any scratches and dents in the car’s body. Then he records the scratches and dents’ places on the manual inspection form that contains the general body of a car, while the customer can take a copy of this form. Figure 1 shows the manual inspection form. Wide-spread car ownership within western societies has led to the dominant paradigm where nearly all adults who can drive and afford a car do own a car and drive it most of the time.²³It allows an assessment of the effectiveness of different policy instruments, market conditions (vehicle supply, private vs fleet market, vehicle segments) and social factors (consumer awareness, range “anxiety”, perceived charging requirements) on different consumer segments, thus providing more policy-focused conclusions on the likely pathways to high penetration of plug-in vehicles that may be required to meet future carbon and air quality targets.

II.OBJECTIVE

1. To transform the manual process of hiring car to a computerized system.
2. To validate the rental system using user satisfaction test.
3. To produce the documentation such as Software requirement specification (SRS), Software Design Description (SSD) as system development references.

SCOPE

The system will be done according to the scope of Online Car Rental System(OCRS).

SYSTEM

1. Provide Car catalog for users as an alternative for them to select car if they want to choose car by their own.
2. Allow admin to search user information from the database based on the users ID Card number or their name.
3. Allow Admin to add a new car.
4. Allow admin to manage booking of car.
5. Allow admin to give car on rent to the proper and legal customers.
6. Allow the user to view feedback and enquiries posted by users.

USER

1. All authorized users can access the system.
2. Allow the user to view information of available car.
3. Allow the user to enquire about the car.
4. Allow the user to book a car.
5. Allow the user to easily get a car on rent.
6. Allow the user to give feedback.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Car-Sharing There are (at least) three distinct forms of car sharing: **Station-based/return car sharing:** Cars are available upon reservation (either months or minutes in advance) at Stations, with electronic access and must be returned to the same station. The service generally offers a wide range of car types to meet various needs. This is generally professionally organized. Some of the better-known providers include Zipcar, Cambior, Flintier and Green wheels. **One-way or 'free-floating' car sharing:** Cars are found on public street space and are available for spontaneous use via smart phone reservation. Cars need not be returned to the same spot but within the defined area of operation. The largest 'free floating' services are operated by the motor industry in conjunction with car rental companies: Car2Go (Mercedes, Europcar), Drive Now (BMW, Six). Auto Lib' in Paris, a fully electric car sharing system, initiated by the battery producer Bolloré. It offers one-way station-to-station car sharing within its operational area. Cars must be returned to AutoLib' stations for charging purposes. **Peer-to-peer car sharing:** Mainly

privately-owned cars are made available by their owners, via Internet platforms (e.g. Tamyca in Germany) or within cooperative systems (e.g. Autopia in Flanders, Belgium). Certain Effect means that people tend to overweight the values of certain events and underestimate the values of uncertainty ones. Influenced by such a tendency, in front of a high probability event, the decision makers are risk-averse over alternatives involving gains, and they become risk-seeking over alternatives involving losses. First, consider the following example concerning gains: ? Alternative (a): a 100% chance of winning \$3000 ? Alternative (b): a 80% chance of winning \$4000, and a 20% chance of winning nothing.

Certain Effect means that people tend to overweight the values of certain events and underestimate the values of uncertainty ones. Influenced by such a tendency, in front of a high probability event, There are two main groups in the car sharing and bike sharing systems, namely round-trip system and one-way system. In round-trip systems, users have to return vehicles to the same station at which the vehicles were picked up. The one-way system offers users the flexibility to return vehicles to stations different from the stations at which the vehicles were picked up. In contrast to round-trip systems, a major operational problem in one-way systems corresponds to the vehicle stock imbalance problem due to asymmetric OD demand. A very common solution to the vehicle stock imbalance problem involves vehicle relocation by employing drivers to relocate vehicles to high demand ports. However, it significantly increases the operational cost of the service providers. This section considers the travel behavior of the users of shared mobility services such as car sharing. For the purposes of simplicity, we first disregard the road network and focus only on trips between the points of origin and destination (OD) The idle times of the fleet provide another indication, if some part

of the fleet is parked in the wrong spots and therefore certain bikes are not used⁵. the decision makers are risk-averse over alternatives involving gains, and they become risk- seeking over alternatives involving losses. First, consider the following example concerning gains: ? Alternative (a): a 100% chance of winning \$3000 ? Alternative (b): a 80% chance of winning \$4000, and a 20% chance of winning nothing.

III METHODOLOGY

The project (Car Rental Portal) is developed by using:-

- FRONT-END:- PHP(Hypertext Preprocessor)
- BACK-END:- MySQL

Introduction to Php: PHP, which stands for “PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor”, is an HTML-embedded scripting language. Much of its syntax

is borrowed from C, Java and Perl with a couple of unique PHP-specific features thrown in. The goal of the language is to allow web developers to write dynamically generated pages quickly. Example 1.1An introductory example

```
<html>
<head>
<title>Example</title>
</head>
<body>
<?php
echo “Hi, I’m a PHP script!”;
?>
</body>
</html>
```

JavaScript:

Java script is embedded into HTML documents and is executed with in them. Java script is browser dependent.JavaScript is an interpreted language that can be interpreted by the browser at run time. Java script is loosely typed language. Java script is an object-based language.Java script is an Event-Driven language and supports event handlers to specify the functionality of a button.JavaScript is a high-level, dynamic, untyped, and interpreted programming language. It has been standardized in the ECMAScript language specification.

Example An introductory example

```
var sum = function() {
    var i, x = 0;
    for (i = 0; i < arguments.length; ++i) {
        x += arguments[i];
    }
    return x;
}
```

sum(1, 2, 3); // returns 6

Introduction to Mysql:

MYSQL is a high performance, relational database server based on MYSQL. It is built on CLIENT/SERVER architecture, which means a frontend or client component, and a back end, or server component. MySQL serverforms the back-end component in this architecture

and is responsible for providing all the standard DBMS functions. The client component, for which there are many different possibilities, is responsible for providing all of the user interface and application-processing function. The language used to communicate between clients and database.

HTML

HyperText Markup Language, commonly abbreviated as HTML, is the standard markup language used to create web pages. Along with CSS, and JavaScript, HTML is a cornerstone technology used to create web pages, as well as to create user interfaces for mobile and web applications. Web browsers can read HTML files and render them into visible or audible web pages. HTML describes the structure of a website semantically and, before the advent of Cascading Style Sheets (CSS), included cues for the presentation or appearance of the document (web page), making it a markup language, rather than a programming language.

Example An introductory example

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>
<head>
<title>This is a title</title>
<body>
<p>Hello world!</p>
</body></html>
```

CSS

Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) is a style sheet language used for describing the presentation of a document written in a markup language. Although most often used to set the visual style of web pages and user interfaces written in HTML and XHTML, the language can be applied to any XML document, including plain XML, SVG and XUL, and is applicable to rendering in speech, or on other media. Along with HTML and JavaScript, CSS is a cornerstone technology used by most websites to create visually engaging webpages, user interfaces for web applications, and user interfaces for many mobile applications.

MODULES:

The system after careful analysis has been identified to be presented with the following modules and roles. The modules involved are:

1. Administrator
2. Users⁷

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

In the system analysis phase the proposed system is defined. In some cases the project management may decide to develop a prototype of the system to demonstrate the understanding of the user requirements and the functionality that will be provided in the proposed system. Structured analysis is the blueprint of a computer system solution to a problem. Or we can say that Structured analysis is the activity of deriving a structured model of the requirements of a system.

Feasibility study is test of a system proposal according to its workability, impact on the organization, ability to meet user needs and effective use of resources. All the projects are feasible given unlimited resources and infinite time! Ergo, feasibility study means an evaluation of benefits versus costs incurred in developing project, where cost includes manpower, time, resources and money.

A purpose of feasibility study is to check out the possibility of a computerized solution to the organization's observed problem before very much money that has been spent on.

A feasibility study is carried out to select the best system that meets performance requirements. Only by spending the time to evaluate the feasibility do I reduce the chances for extreme embarrassment at later stage of the system project.

TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY :-

Technical analysis evaluates technical merits of the system at the same time collecting additional information about performance, reliability, maintainability and productivity. In some cases, this system analysis step also

includes a limited amount of research and design.

The proposed system has system capacity of required to hold data. This project is efficient and responds quickly for various enquires regardless of number of locations. The system proposed should be expanded easily and efficiency, whenever required.

Requirement	How Accomplished?
Front end	HTML, DHTML, JavaScript
Back end	MySQL
Technology used	PHP
Server	Apache
Documentation Tools	Macromedia Dream weaver MX, Edit plus, Microsoft FrontPage
Communication Tools	Intranet/Internet

From the formulation of the questionnaire, the concept of sharing a car owned by the household is rather wide in several respects. First, the "other driver" occasionally using the car is not necessarily part of the household. Second, the structure of the questionnaire survey refers to the last twelve months: so sharing the car can occur occasionally or regularly; it can correspond to the loan of a car for certain trips (or purposes), but also with the division of the driving task during a long trip that can be more often seen for the main vehicle and in the case of departure on holiday. Besides, only drivers sharing the car are considered here, passengers are not turning cars into shared cars.

V. THREATS TO SYSTEM SECURITY

A procedure for protecting systems makes sure that the facility is physically secure, provides a recovery/restart capability, and has access to backup files. If we list in order of probability the threats to system security or data integrity, research shows that the most damage comes from errors and omissions—people making mistakes. The threat of external attack on a computer system is virtually last. This means that in establishing a priority sequence, one would probably want to start from within the firm and work out. The list of potential threats is:

- I. Errors and omissions.
- II. Disgruntled and dishonest employees.
- III. Fire
- IV. Natural Disasters
- V. External attack

III. Conclusions

Car sharing has huge potential to improve quality of life and traffic conditions in cities. This includes looking at the inclusion of autonomous transport systems, the impacts they can have on the urban environment in conjunction with (station-based) car sharing models and the infrastructure needs they present. As a result, it was possible to interpret the auction mechanism for mobility sharing as an exchange economy based on the trip's OD demand between users. Given the single-minded bidding case, the efficient solution method in multiple bidding case was proposed. Therefore, the two problems in a mobility sharing auction were solved. For each time slice on a specific day, our demand model and the relocation algorithm provide the optimal fleet distribution and a relocation recommendation.

To test and prove the given methodology, a validation was carried out for each zone to capture the impact not only in a short time sense (meaning the following time slice) but also the dynamics that follow due to the different fleet distribution the entire day. Examination of the statistical results obtained for the different types of stations show that the operational characteristics of the stations studied in this paper are relevant to the station attributes, but the connection is not obvious. This paper presents some of our preliminary investigations of applicability of the Prospect Theory on product service system. Using car sharing service as an illustrative example of user-oriented PSS, we explained how the Certainty, Probability, and Reflection effects in the Prospect Theory can be used to explain people's irrational decision making over product (i.e., car owning) and services (i.e., car sharing and car renting), as well as over different kinds of car sharing service plans.

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